

IoT Aided Congestion Avoidance in Emergency Evacuation

1st Erol Gelenbe

Institute of Theoretical and Applied Informatics
Polish Academy of Science, Gliwice
& Dept. of Engineering, Kings College London

2nd Yuting Ma

Hubei University of Automotive Technology, Shiyan, China
IITIS-PAN, Gliwice, Poland
15985836383@163.com

Abstract—Efficient and reliable evacuation management during emergency situations becomes very challenging, particularly in spatially constrained environments such as passenger ships. Recent advances in the Internet of Things (IoT) provide new opportunities to improve evacuation safety and efficiency through real-time sensing, communication, and decision-making. In this paper, an IoT-assisted evacuation framework is studied using an analytical queueing network model. A Pull-based evacuation policy is proposed, in which evacuees are instructed to proceed only after preceding evacuees have exited the evacuation system, thereby mitigating congestion propagation along the downstream corridors, stairways, and passageways. The proposed policy relies on active IoT devices to deliver real-time visual and auditory guidance, including waiting, movement, and routing instructions. The effectiveness of the IoT-based Pull Policy is evaluated through a realistic case study of evacuation on a commercial cruise ship. The queueing network formulation enables computationally efficient performance analysis and systematic comparison of multiple routing strategies under heterogeneous evacuee walking speeds, and shows that the proposed approach significantly reduces congestion and enhances overall evacuation efficiency.

Index Terms—Emergency Evacuation; Internet of Things; Cruise Ships; G-Networks

I. INTRODUCTION

The effective management of large-scale emergencies is a long-standing research topic, motivated by the need to minimise loss of life, reduce injuries, and mitigate economic and infrastructure damage. Emergency situations arise frequently worldwide including wildfires [1], hurricanes [2], floods [3], and accidents in public venues such as theatres, stadiums, and transportation hubs [4]. Recent events worldwide highlight the vulnerability of civilian populations and the essential role of timely rescue and evacuation. Despite the diversity of emergency scenarios, all evacuation processes share several common characteristics: (i) they typically occur in spatially constrained environments—such as buildings, road networks, or transportation systems, where congestion can easily form due to restricted movement, (ii) evacuation often involves heterogeneous populations, comprising able-bodied individuals as well as children, elderly passengers, and injured persons who may require assistance, and (iii) emergency responders must operate concurrently with evacuees, frequently under hazardous conditions involving fire, smoke, toxic gases, or structural instability, making evacuation management a complex cyber-physical problem requiring rapid, reliable, and adaptive decision support.

To address these challenges, extensive research has focused on the design of specialised cyber-physical systems such as the IoT [5], [6] and advanced algorithmic methods [7], [8]. Moreover, given the highly distributed nature of evacuation processes with numerous autonomous human agents interacting with each other and with a dynamically evolving environment, both analytical models and simulation techniques [9], including agent-based [10], [11] discrete event simulations [12], have been developed and used to assess the evacuation performance in terms of evacuation time, congestion levels, survival probability, and responder access times. On the other hand, only few experimental studies have also been conducted concerning the value of guidance and signage systems for building evacuation [13], [14]. Evacuation on cruise ships has attracted increasing attention due to their potentially catastrophic consequences [15]. Current international regulations require cruise ships to provide static evacuation plans that specify predefined routes to muster stations [16]. However, such plans are inherently limited, as they cannot adapt to real-time conditions such as congestion, blocked passageways, or uneven passenger distributions. Recent advances in Internet of Things (IoT) technologies have enabled new possibilities for adaptive evacuation management on ships [17]. Sensor networks can monitor crowd congestion and environmental dynamics, while communication systems can provide real-time guidance through visual and auditory signals.

In this paper, we investigate how passenger routing and scheduling policies [18], [19] influence evacuation performance on cruise ships, with respect to evacuation time and congestion, under heterogeneous walking speeds, using a G-network-based [20] queueing model that enables fast and accurate computation. In addition, we introduce an IoT-enabled Pull Policy, in which passenger movements are regulated based on messages triggered by exit events of preceding passengers. By synchronizing passenger entry from waiting areas into evacuation paths with the exit of previously scheduled evacuees, the proposed policy can mitigate crowd congestion and reduce overall evacuation delay. The remainder of the paper is organised as follows. Section II elaborates on the analytical model adopted in this study. Section III introduces the Pull Policy, and Section IV presents numerical results concerning the evacuation performance of this policy and a heuristic variant under different routing rules. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and discusses directions for future

research.

II. ANALYTICAL MODEL

The evacuation system consists of a finite set of locations traversed by evacuees from their initial entry points to the exits, the corridors and staircases connecting these locations, and a set of exit points through which evacuees leave the vessel. This structure is modelled as a directed acyclic graph (DAG) $G = (V, A)$, where $V = \{1, \dots, n\}$ is the set of nodes representing physical locations, and $A(i, j)$ denotes a directed arc corresponding to a corridor or staircase that allows movement from node i to node j during an emergency evacuation. For any pair of nodes (i, j) , at most one directed arc, either $A(i, j)$ or $A(j, i)$, may exist, and self-loops are excluded. Accordingly, the adjacency matrix $A = [A(i, j)]_{n \times n}$ satisfies

$$A(i, i) = 0, A(i, j)A(j, i) = 0, \quad \forall i \in V. \quad (1)$$

The node set V is partitioned into three disjoint subsets: the set of source nodes S , the set of exit (sink) nodes F , and the set of intermediate nodes I , $V = S \cup F \cup I$, where:

$$S = \{i \mid A(j, i) = 0, F = \{i \mid A(i, j) = 0, j \neq i\}, \quad (2)$$

All remaining nodes belong to the set of intermediate nodes I . To ensure evacuation feasibility, we assume that the graph G has an important property: from any node in V , at least one exit node in F can be reached by traversing no more than $n - 1$ directional arcs. This assumption guarantees that every evacuee can reach an exit through at most $n - 1$ passageways or staircases. To evaluate the average evacuation delay experienced by an evacuee from a source node to an exit node, we model the evacuation system as a network of queues. Each queue is assumed to have infinite buffer capacity, implying that corridors, passageways, and staircases are sufficiently large and therefore never become physically saturated.

A. Arrivals, Services and Routing at Intermediate Passageways

Each source node $s \in S$ represents a corridor K_s through which evacuees exit individual cabins or common spaces (e.g., restaurants or lounges) and move toward a waiting area H_s . Arrivals of evacuees into corridor K_s are assumed to follow a Poisson process with rate λ_s . Evacuees traverse corridor K_s in an average time τ_s and subsequently join a First-In-First-Out (FIFO) queue at waiting area H_s . For a corridor of length L_s with C_s cabins distributed along its sides, and assuming an average walking speed v (m/s), the mean traversal time is:

$$\tau_s = 0.5 L_s v^{-1}. \quad (3)$$

Assuming that each cabin along corridor K_s accommodates evacuees who exit their cabins individually, then arrival rate into K_s is:

$$\lambda_s = \frac{C_s}{\tau_s} = \frac{2vC_s}{L_s}. \quad (4)$$

For any arc such that $A(i, j) = 1$, the corresponding corridor, passageway, or staircase $K(i, j)$, where $i \in S \cup I$ and $j \in I \cup F$, is modeled as a FIFO queue with independent and exponentially distributed service times with mean μ_{ij}^{-1} . If node j is an intermediate node, an evacuee departing from $K(i, j)$ is routed to a downstream queue $K(j, l)$ such that $A(j, l) = 1$ with probability $P(j, l)$. The routing probabilities satisfy:

$$\sum_{l \in I \cup F} A(j, l)P(j, l) = 1. \quad (5)$$

At each exit node $f \in F$, evacuees depart the system through a final passageway K_f , modeled as a FIFO queue with independent and identically distributed exponential service times of exit rate β_f .

III. ROUTING OF EVACUEES

This section first introduces four rules for routing evacuees after an *evacuation order* has been issued, and then elaborates on the proposed Pull Policy, which controls admission from waiting areas into downstream passageways to mitigate congestion. Evacuees select outgoing links according to one of the following four *Path Selection Rules*, applied at all non-exit nodes.

- 1) **Path Selection Rule 1:** An evacuee leaving node i disregards the relative speeds of the successor links and selects any outgoing link $K(i, j)$, $j \in S(i)$, with equal probability. Formally,

$$P(i, j) = \frac{1}{|S(i)|}, \quad |S(i)| > 0. \quad (6)$$

- 2) **Path Selection Rule 2:** An evacuee selects the outgoing link with the largest service rate, i.e.,

$$\mu_{ic} \geq \mu_{ij}, \quad \forall j \in S(i). \quad (7)$$

If multiple such links exist, the link with the smallest value of j is selected.

- 3) **Path Selection Rule 3:** An evacuee leaving node i selects successor link $K(i, c)$ with probability

$$P(i, c) = \frac{\mu_{ic}}{\sum_{k \in S(i)} \mu_{ik}}. \quad (8)$$

As shown in Section III-A, this rule yields an important performance result: the average delay on each outgoing link is identical and equivalent to that of a virtual link whose service rate is the average of the service rates of all the outgoing links, and whose incoming traffic rate corresponds to an equal share of the total traffic rate across these links.

- 4) **Path Selection Rule 4:** Evacuees select the path to an exit that minimises the total expected evacuation time while ensuring that a predefined deadline is not violated under worst-case link delays. Shortest paths can be computed using Dijkstra's algorithm [21] or its variants [22], with computational complexity $O(n^2)$ for a graph of n nodes.

In the context of cruise ship evacuation, worst-case link delays are conservatively estimated based on corridor length and walking speed under a ship heel angle of 20° . The evacuation deadline is defined as

$$D = 0.8 \left(T_S - \frac{2}{3} T_{EL} \right) - T_A, \quad (9)$$

where T_S is the estimated survival time until ship capsizing, T_{EL} is the total embarkation and launching time, T_A is the passenger awareness and reaction time, and 0.8 is a safety factor. It is worth noting that all four Path Selection Rules rely on fixed, *a priori* decision mechanisms and do not require local computation or communication at individual nodes. Communication is only required for the Pull Policy and the Pull Heuristic discussed below.

A. Key Property of Path Selection Rule 3

Under Path Selection Rule 3, passengers enter link $K(i, c)$ with probability $P(i, c)$ in FIFO order. Assuming exponential service times with mean μ_{ic}^{-1} , the average time spent on link $K(i, c)$ can be computed using the results in [20]:

$$W_{ic} = \frac{1}{\mu_{ic} - \lambda_i P(i, c)}. \quad (10)$$

The average delay experienced across all outgoing links from node i is then:

$$\sum_{c \in S(i)} P(i, c) W_{ic} = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{|S(i)|} \sum_{k \in S(i)} \mu_{ik} \frac{\lambda_i}{|S(i)|}}, \quad (11)$$

which, very interestingly, is equivalent to the average delay of a single service center with a service rate equal to the average of the service rates of all outgoing links from node i , and an incoming traffic rate equal to λ_i , divided by the number of outgoing links.

B. The Pull Policy

Under the *Baseline Policy*, once an evacuee reaches a node where an outgoing passageway must be chosen, she immediately proceeds according to a predefined Path Selection Rule, without any waiting or synchronization. No explicit congestion control is applied, and evacuees are allowed to enter downstream links as soon as they arrive at their entrances. In contrast, we introduce a controlled admission mechanism referred to as the *Pull Policy*. In this case, evacuees exiting cabins or common spaces initially wait in designated waiting areas. They are admitted into the evacuation system in FIFO order, following a predefined Path Selection Rule, only after receiving an explicit signal to proceed into the passageways. The motivation for this policy is that unrestricted entry into passageways can lead to severe congestion, whereas regulated admission can smooth passenger flow and mitigate congestion buildup.

The Pull Policy assumes the availability of a wired or wireless communication mechanism whereby an exit node generates and sends a message upstream to a waiting area upon the departure of an evacuee from an exit. The receiving waiting area is chosen uniformly at random. In contrast, under

the *Pull Heuristic*, the message is broadcast simultaneously to all waiting areas, thereby reducing idle waiting times at the expense of potentially increased downstream congestion. Additionally, we introduce another variant of the Pull Policy, termed the *Weighted Pull Policy*, under which the probability that a waiting area H_s receives the message from an exit node is:

$$p(f, s) = \frac{\lambda_s}{\sum_{s \in S} \lambda_s}. \quad (12)$$

The implementation of the Pull Policy does not require complicated technologies. For example, it can be realized using SMS messaging on mobile devices. The specific technologies adopted depend on the available infrastructure, budget constraints, and whether the evacuation process is intended to operate fully autonomously or under human control. Formally, the Pull Policy operates in the evacuation system as follows:

- When an evacuee exits the system through an exit node $f \in F$, a message is sent to all waiting areas H_s at the sources with probabilities $p(f, s) = \frac{1}{|S|}$, which satisfy $\sum_{s \in S} p(f, s) = 1$.
- Upon receiving a message, if the waiting area H_s is non-empty, the evacuee at the head of its FIFO queue immediately enters the evacuation system and selects an outgoing link according to the prescribed Path Selection Rule.
- Each waiting area H_s is associated with an impatience time with mean $1/\alpha_s$, after which the evacuee at the head of the queue proceeds into the evacuation system even if no pull message has been received by H_s from any exit node f .
- The Weighted Pull Policy is also assessed, in which an exit node sends a message to each waiting area H_s with probability $p(f, s) = \frac{\lambda_s}{\sum_{s \in S} \lambda_s}$, where the probabilities satisfy $\sum_{s \in S} p(f, s) = 1$. The Weighted Pull Policy assigns higher probabilities of receiving the message to waiting areas that are occupied by evacuees.
- We also evaluate the Pull Heuristic, in which an exit node broadcasts messages simultaneously to all waiting areas. This is modeled by setting $p(f, s) = 1$ for all $s \in S$. The purpose of the Pull heuristic is to reduce the likelihood that a message is sent to a waiting area where there are no evacuees.

The term *Baseline Model* is used hereafter to denote the system without the Pull Policy, the Weighted Pull Policy or the Pull Heuristic, in which evacuees immediately select and enter outgoing links upon arrival at nodes where a routing decision is required.

C. Analytical Solution

The analysis assumes that passengers arrive into the source nodes (or waiting areas) according to a Poisson process of rate λ_s , and we make no further assumptions about the arrival processes at any of the other nodes that are down-stream from the source nodes. The resulting queueing network can be analyzed as a special case of G-Networks with triggered

customer movement [20]. Let Q_s , $0 \leq Q_s < 1$, denote the steady-state probability that waiting area H_s is non-empty, and let Q_f , $0 \leq Q_f < 1$ denote the probability that exit node f is busy. We then have

$$Q_s = \frac{\lambda_s}{\alpha_s + \sum_{f \in F} Q_f \beta_f p(f, s)}, \quad s \in S. \quad (13)$$

and

$$Q_f = \frac{\lambda_f}{\beta_f}, \quad f \in F. \quad (14)$$

The passenger flow rates into each intermediate and exit node are determined by solving the following linear equations:

$$\lambda_i = \sum_{s \in S} \mathbf{1}[s = i] \lambda_s + \sum_{l \in I} \lambda_l A(l, i) P(l, i), \quad i \in I, \quad (15)$$

$$\lambda_f = \sum_{s \in S} \lambda_s A(s, f) P(s, f) + \sum_{l \in I} \lambda_l A(l, f) P(l, f), \quad f \in F, \quad (16)$$

where λ_s , $s \in S$, is obtained from (4). The flow rates are then used to compute:

$$q_{ij} = \frac{\lambda_i P(i, j)}{\mu_{ij}}, \quad Q_f = \frac{\lambda_f}{\beta_f},$$

where q_{ij} denotes the steady-state probability that $K(i, j)$ contains at least one evacuee. Now N , the average number of evacuees in the system. It is given by:

$$N = \sum_{s \in S} [\tau_s + \frac{Q_s}{1 - Q_s}] + \sum_{f \in F} \frac{Q_f}{1 - Q_f} + \sum_{i, j=1, i \neq j}^n A(i, j) \frac{q_{ij}}{1 - q_{ij}}, \quad (17)$$

and by Little's Law [23], [24], the average total time spent by an evacuee in the system, denoted by W , is:

$$W = \frac{N}{\lambda}, \quad \text{with } \lambda = \sum_{s \in S} \lambda_s. \quad (18)$$

Note that the arrival rates λ_s , $s \in S$, are computed in $O(|S|)$ time. The remaining flow rates are obtained by solving the $n - |S|$ linear equations (15) and (16). Since G is acyclic, these equations can be solved in $O((n - |S|)^2)$ time. As we need to store the connectivity information for G , the space complexity for solving the model is $O(n^2)$. That is, the computation time and memory requirements scale quadratically with n , exhibiting low polynomial complexity, and the model is solved using a conventional linear equation solver. It is also worth noting that both the Pull Policy and the Weighted Pull Policy require only a single message per exiting passenger from an exit, whereas the Pull Heuristic with S waiting areas generates and sends $|S|$ messages per passenger exiting the system.

(a) The second deck of the Yangtze Gold 7 cruise ship.

(b) The third deck of the Yangtze Gold 7 cruise ship.

(c) The fourth deck of the Yangtze Gold 7 cruise ship.

Fig. 1: Graph model of the simulated environment.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The numerical evaluation of system performance can now be performed using a realistic evacuation environment based on the second, third, and fourth decks of the *Yangtze Gold 7* cruise ship. The environment is modelled as a directed graph with 347 nodes and 528 edges, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Passage ways on the second, third, and fourth decks are represented by blue, green, and red edges, respectively. Additionally, there are ten staircases connecting the decks.

The graph model contains a single exit node, indicated by a red triangle. Cabin locations are represented as yellow circles, and all other intermediate nodes are shown as black squares. Each node is labeled with a unique identifier. The traversal delay of each edge is estimated based on its physical length and the average walking speed of evacuees on a cruise ship under normal conditions. Following IMO MSC.1/Circular.1533 [16], the walking speed on flat corridors is set to 0.56 m/s, while the speeds for descending and ascending staircases are 0.45 m/s

and 0.37 m/s, respectively. Additionally, for the Yangtze Gold 7 cruise ship, $T_S = 80$ minutes, $T_{EL} = 30$ minutes, and $T_A = 10$ minutes under night-time scenarios. Therefore, the evacuation deadline D is set to 40 minutes for Path Selection Rule 4. The key parameters associated with the source nodes and the exit node are summarized in Table I.

TABLE I: Parameters regarding the source nodes and the exit node.

Source/Exit Node Identity	Corridor Length L_s (m)	Cabin Number C_s	Avg. Inter-Exit Time for f (s)
Source 21	76	38	1.786
Source 31	80	31	
Source 32	26	9	
Source 33	26	9	
Source 41	64	33	
Source 42	26	9	
Source 43	26	9	
Exit 21			

A. Evaluation of the Pull Policy

We evaluate the effectiveness of the Pull Policy by comparing the average total time an evacuee spends in the evacuation system with those obtained using the Baseline Model, the Weighted Pull Policy, and the Pull Heuristic, as shown in Fig. 2. The comparison is conducted under all four Path Selection Rules, with $\lambda = 0.027$. The results demonstrate that exit-triggered signaling consistently improves overall evacuation efficiency. In addition, Path Selection Rule 4 yields the lowest average total time spent in the system for all three algorithms, as congestion effects are negligible at the lower total arrival rate $\lambda = 0.027$, and the rule effectively selects the path with the shortest typical delay to the exit while satisfying the deadline constraint.

Fig. 2: Comparison of the average total time spent in the system under all three algorithms and the four Path Selection Rules when $\alpha_s = 0.035$ and $\lambda = 0.027$.

In practice, the number of evacuees occupying different cabins can vary, leading to different arrival rates at the source nodes. This section investigates evacuation performance in terms of the average total number of evacuees and the average total time in the system under varying total arrival rates, with λ ranging from $\lambda = 0.014$ to $\lambda = 0.184$ in increments of 0.013. When $\lambda = 0.197$, the system becomes unstable for all

algorithms and Path Selection Rules. In this set of experiments, the waiting-area service rate is set to $\alpha_s = 0.125\beta_f = 0.07$.

Fig. 3: Average total time in the system versus the total passenger arrival rate λ at the source nodes, using the three algorithms across all four Path Selection Rules with $\alpha_s = 0.07$.

Fig. 3 presents the average total time in the system as functions of λ . As λ increases, both metrics grow increasingly rapidly and culminate at a critical threshold beyond which the system becomes saturated. The saturation threshold is strongly influenced by the Path Selection Rule employed. Specifically, under Path Selection Rule 2, the system becomes unstable at $\lambda = 0.033$ due to congestion on a critical intermediate link (80,78). Path Selection Rule 3 maintains stability over a wider range of total arrival rates owing to its probabilistic load-sharing mechanism. Path Selection Rule 4 achieves the lowest average total number of evacuees and hence the shortest average total time in the system when $\lambda \leq 0.132$, but becomes vulnerable to congestion at higher arrival rates as evacuees increasingly concentrate on the path with the shortest typical delay for a specified deadline. Path Selection Rule 1 exhibits competitive performance at $\lambda = 0.138$ across all three algorithms, while Path Selection Rule 3 outperforms the others when $\lambda > 0.138$. We can also see from Fig. 3 that for all values of λ where system stability is preserved, the Pull Policy, the Weighted Pull Policy, and the Pull Heuristic consistently reduce the average total time in the system compared with the Baseline Model. Fig. 4 further illustrates system performance under a lower waiting-area service rate of $\alpha_s = 0.035$. In this case, instability occurs for the Baseline Model combined with Path Selection Rule 3 when $\lambda > 0.171$, primarily due to congestion at a waiting area on the third deck. The pull-based mechanisms effectively extend system stability to higher arrival rates by regulating downstream admission.

Table II summarizes the saturation thresholds and the corresponding causes of saturation for different algorithms and Path Selection Rules under $\alpha_s = 0.07$ and $\alpha_s = 0.035$.

TABLE II: Saturation thresholds and causes for different algorithms and Path Selection Rules.

Saturation Threshold & Cause	$\alpha_s=0.07$				$\alpha_s=0.035$			
	Baseline Model	Pull Policy	Weighted Pull Policy	Pull Heuristic	Baseline Model	Pull Policy	Weighted Pull Policy	Pull Heuristic
Path Selection Rule 1	0.158&link (22,21)	0.158&link(22,21)	0.158&link(22,21)	0.158&link(22,21)	0.158&link (22,21)	0.158&link(22,21)	0.158&link(22,21)	0.158&link(22,21)
Path Selection Rule 2	0.033&link(80,78)							
Path Selection Rule 3	0.191&link(69,68)	0.191&link(69,68)	0.191&link(69,68)	0.191&link(69,68)	0.178&waiting area	0.191&link(69,68)	0.191&link(69,68)	0.191&link(69,68)
Path Selection Rule 4	0.151&link (211,113)							

Fig. 4: Average total total time in the system versus the total passenger arrival rate λ at the source nodes for all three algorithms across the four Path Selection Rules, with $\alpha_s=0.035$.

B. Impact of Service Rate at Waiting Areas

Finally, we examine the effect of the service rate at waiting areas on evacuation efficiency. The service rate α_s is varied from $\frac{1}{16}\beta_f$ to $\frac{1}{2}\beta_f$, with the upper limit imposed to prevent excessive bursts of evacuees from waiting areas entering into the system that could induce downstream congestion. Figs. 5 show the average total time in the system as a function of the service rate at waiting areas for four representative total arrival rates: $\lambda = 0.014$, $\lambda = 0.033$, $\lambda = 0.151$, and $\lambda = 0.158$. We can see that in all cases, increasing α_s reduces the average total time, although the marginal improvement diminishes at higher values of α_s .

It is worth noting that when $\lambda = 0.014$ and $\lambda = 0.033$, Path Selection Rule 4 achieves the best performance across all algorithms due to the absence of congestion. For $\lambda = 0.033$ and $\lambda = 0.151$, Path Selection Rule 2 and Path Selection Rule 4, respectively, lead to instability, while Path Selection Rules 1 and 3 benefit from load distribution effects. At $\lambda = 0.158$, only Path Selection Rule 3 preserves system stability, highlighting the importance of probabilistic traffic sharing under heavy load conditions. In all scenarios, the Pull Policy, the Weighted Pull Policy, and the Pull Heuristic

significantly reduce average total time in the system compared with the Baseline Model, confirming the effectiveness of exit-triggered admission control.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Ensuring safe, reliable, and timely evacuation is a critical challenge for large transportation systems such as cruise ships and aircraft, where high passenger density, limited space, and complex layouts can significantly hinder emergency response. Current evacuation procedures often rely on pre-planned instructions, which may be inadequate when accounting for dynamic crowd congestion and varying environmental conditions, and heterogeneous passenger behavior.

Thus, in this paper, we have evaluated some congestion-aware evacuation strategies that improve the efficiency of human evacuation, while requiring minimal additional infrastructure. Two complementary mechanisms were investigated. The first focuses on reducing the average total time in the evacuation system through smart routing to distribute evacuees across multiple available paths, thereby leveraging the aggregate capacity of the system. The second mechanism, referred to as the *Pull Policy*, synchronizes the admission of evacuees into downstream passageways with the departure of preceding evacuees from the exits, effectively mitigating bottlenecks and downstream congestion. We also evaluated a Pull Heuristic variant, which simultaneously releases evacuees from all waiting areas upon each passenger exit event.

To analyze these mechanisms, we employed a queueing network model that leverages G-Networks to model exit-triggered admission control in a computationally efficient manner. For the feedforward network model considered in this work, the resulting analytical solution exhibits a computational complexity of $O(n^2)$ and a memory requirement of the same order, making it suitable for very large-scale evacuation scenarios. Numerical results obtained from a realistic case study based on the Yangtze Gold cruise ship show that both the Pull Policy, and the Pull Heuristic, consistently reduce congestion and the average total time in the system across a wide range of operating conditions. While the case study focuses on a cruise ship environment, the proposed policies can be readily applied to other evacuation settings. Future research will focus on developing more adaptive, IoT-enabled control strategies that anticipate congestion and dynamically regulate evacuee flow to maximise throughput while preserving passenger safety. In

(a) $\lambda = 0.014$

(b) $\lambda = 0.158$

Fig. 5: Average total time spent by evacuees in the system versus the service rate at the waiting area for different values of λ .

addition, we plan to investigate the impact of communication delays and failures on system performance and to design robust evacuation control architectures capable of maintaining acceptable performance under partial information or signalling disruptions.

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